

**INDIVIDUAL CHARACTERISTICS OF DEVELOPMENT OF
ECOLOGICAL CULTURE IN STUDENTS
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Annotation. The article deals with the framework of our research, it is important to consider ecological culture in order to implement it in the process of forming high school students and their individual capabilities. Also, in the context of this research, the author says that it is crucial to consider ecological culture when developing high school students and their individual capabilities.

Key words: ecological, culture, high school students, preserve nature, independent thinking, intellectual activity, creative approach.

Introduction. Taking into account the age dynamics of attitude to nature, we agree with the authors that it is the most optimal age for effective education of ecological culture, taking into account the age dynamics of attitude to nature developed by E.M. Akopyan, B. Yakuta [1]. The basics of understanding the laws of development in this age group are in the psychology of patriotism, E.M. Alexandrovskaya, N.V. Vordovskaya, E.O. Turdikulov, A.S. Tokhtayev, A. Hamidov [1]. I.M. Gorbunov says that the child's attitude to the natural world is dynamic. At the age of a schoolboy, the input component of the subjective-nopr pragmatic type of attitude prevails: high school students are attracted by any meaningful activity, they are ready to preserve nature, to interact with it, not only for profit. The crisis of a high school student is understood as a crisis of subjective attitude to nature, the practical objective-pragmatic type sharply comes to the fore [2; 226-b]. According to E.G.Garunov, E.O. Turdikulov, S.D. Researchers such as Abdurakhmanov [3; 70-p] high school students are subject to environmental education.

The peculiarities of the activities of high school students are emphasized by scientists: "authorship of productive activity, search for new types of social activity", "the leading activity of high school students is the formation of new methods in social communication with adults; leading activity of a high school student - as a socially meaningful relationship; as the leading activity of a high school student - intimate-personal relationship" is covered in the researches of I.R. Aleksandrova, Ya.K. Vabansky, A.G. Vannikov [3]. A high school student strives for a quick result, it is important for him to see the result of his next action, to

discuss it with his peers, to satisfy the need for self-expression, which is manifested in a sharp increase in his reflexes as a reflection of the internal situation of his feelings. It is important for this age group to receive the evaluation of others. From this comes the orientation to work similar to the work done by adults, the search for activities that give real benefits and receive community value. High school students should have the opportunity to feel themselves at a real adult age during the transition period (15-17 years old).

The team of authors Z.P.Vasilsova, G.N.Volkov, F.M.Galiyeva believe that students of the upper class should create various conditions for them to feel themselves at an older age, as well as to determine the lack of their abilities and their limits. Such situations can be realized by significantly restructuring the interaction of high school students with teachers and classmates, for example, by special methods of cooperation and supervision and assessment among students of different age groups [3]. In this period, effective differentiation of important activities can be manifested - from education and social activities to petty activities and anti-society activities. He believes that as an internal criterion of differentiation, look for a successful, if not successful, free, that is, independent type of activity in the child. In ecological activities, an ecological culture suitable for the characteristics of the formation of the personality of a high school student during the physical lesson is brought up. So, in the process of personality development, the ecological culture of high school students is determined.

In this period, the emotional sphere of a high school student is characterized by openness, strength, immediacy, stability. In his relationship with nature, his emotional relationship comes to the fore, but this relationship does not have unity, because it is "scattered" in various educational subjects. At this age, writes Kha.A. Rakhmatova, there are difficulties in communication, including closedness, negativity, conflict, emotional imbalance, lack of confidence in one's own strength, anxiety and restlessness. Taking into account these characteristics, in addition to the establishment of special relationships between pedagogues and high school students, it is necessary to pay attention to the organization of communication with peers, which is provided through special (for example, project and research) forms of learning [4].

The period of a high school student is a pleasant period for gaining cognitive activity and curiosity, despite the instability of his emotional sphere. Their interests are unstable and multidirectional, and develop in the direction of seeking novelty. Abstractness, theoretical thinking, purposefulness of reception, stability, attention and speech-logical recall are formed. The ability to make

complex conclusions, put forward hypotheses and construct their verification is developed. In this period, individuality is strongly felt in intellectual activity, which is associated with the development of independent thinking, intellectual activity, creative approach to solving tasks. This makes it possible to consider 15-16 years as a sensitive period for the development of creative thinking. Taking into account these characteristics, it is appropriate to use them in the implementation of abilities, to determine the scope of their permanent interests in the ecological field, especially in solving environmental problems.

During the research activity, the increase in motivation is high, low, and conscious. This is helped by the motive of knowledge, which is aimed at the acquisition of new research knowledge presented by him, and determines the direction in the study of the methods of the motive of knowledge, which stimulates the activity of contributing to the motive of acquiring and acquiring new knowledge.

Kh.A.Rakhmatova expresses a different opinion about the educational activities of high school students. He emphasizes that the attitude to academic activity and academic motivation of a high school student is two-sided and even somewhat paradoxical.

On the one hand, this period is characterized by a decrease in educational motivation, which is explained by an increase in interest in the environment outside the school and by being obsessed with communicating with peers. On the other hand, as mentioned above, this period is sensitive for the formation of new, mature learning motivations. If reading has a personal quality, it becomes an activity of independent learning and self-improvement. The decrease in learning motivation is partly caused by the inability of high school students to see the meaning of learning. Evaluating school knowledge does not capture their vision of growing up. It is important to include the leading motives of a high school student: communication and self-awareness for the development of educational motivation. In this position, along with the development of motives for self-awareness, the development of motives for emotional acceptance of environmental values is carried out [4].

According to K.A. Rakhmatova, the important psychological foundations of high school students consist of reflexive "self-focus". The reflexive attitude to opportunities and abilities in educational activities is transferred to the sphere of self-awareness, in which the process of accepting that he is no longer a child begins to take place. In this case, a number of successive stages are passed in the child's growth: from the discovery of the adult image to independence and

responsibility, to the understanding of the limits of personal growth with the given level. This leads to the creation of relationships in the measure of one's personal capabilities and abilities, that is, a reflexive attitude to the sought-after growth [4].

Based on the above, we note that the characteristics of the age of a high school student: the formation of interests, inner world, personal reflection, abstract-logical, the opening of learning to self-analysis and the desire to understand oneself in a realistic manner are new types of this age.

Knowledge and conditions of their application in pedagogical practice, including social responsibility in the value structure of adolescents' obligations in school life, school activities that allow adolescents to expand their knowledge, experience socially responsible actions, organize school life taking into account common interests, choosing between one's socially responsible actions and one's personality, the social orientation of responsibility, which allows to increase the level of creation of pedagogical situations - making judgments about social responsibility, enriching social experience, relying on the positive feelings of responsible behavior and experience. will be a guarantee of a more successful process in educating students of ecological culture.

Conclusion. Thus, community's educational potential is prioritized, youth's voluntary and free perception of free time is a space that can be used for self-expression and recognition, and secondly, leisure activities are inherently capable personal additional space is needed to cover and create the missing elements of development, self-awareness and recognition, only within the framework of environmental education, orientation to the development of the individual helps to form stable aspects, the correct orientation is the natural environment activities that provide an opportunity to acquire communication skills with people focused on care, nature, teamwork, create valuable personal qualities, communication, determination, patience, feelings of mutual help, tourism resist harmful habits (smoking) (alcohol, etc.) provides an opportunity to build a strong foundation for healthy beliefs. It becomes clear that the aforementioned components of ecological culture require a more structured narrative approach. On the basis of the theoretical analysis of the problem under consideration, we developed the elements of the development of ecological culture in high school students of medium and high levels.

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